

TEACHING METHODOLOGY FOR BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

Nazarova Markhabo Sharibjonovna

Teacher Of Vocational School No. 1 Dangarinsky District.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11664874>

Abstract: This article provides information about the methodology of teaching biology and the principles of the educational process.

Key words: Methods of teaching biology, principles, educational material, educational process, subject, lesson, personality, forms of teaching.

Biology teaching methodology is the science of learning, processes, principles and laws related to the fundamentals of biology. Knowledge of these principles and patterns allows the teacher to organize and manage educational processes related to the school biology course in accordance with the requirements of the time. The methodology of teaching biology is aimed at an interdependent presentation of the content of biology subjects, forms of teaching, methods and tools.

The main objective of biology teaching methods is to provide students with in-depth knowledge of biological subjects, to develop the content of subjects, forms of teaching, tools and methods that help them grow as a comprehensively developed individual. Methods of teaching biology as a science Any science is related to human research activities, it is aimed at collecting knowledge about things and phenomena, and the thing being studied is about the phenomena in full and is aimed at obtaining deep knowledge. The main function of science is research.

The methodology for teaching biology as a science is aimed at studying the training, education and development of students related to this science from a theoretical and practical point of view. The main feature of science is clarity of purpose, subject of study, methods and forms of knowledge. At the same time, it is important to know the history of the development of science, the discoveries that led to its enrichment. The methodology of teaching biology is part of pedagogical science. For this reason, the goals and objectives facing him arise from general pedagogical goals and objectives.

The methodology of teaching biology is aimed at applying pedagogical rules applicable to all academic subjects to biological educational material. In addition, the methodology of teaching biology includes natural, scientific, biological, psychological, and pedagogical knowledge. The effectiveness of teaching biology in the modern period is determined by the acquisition by students of biological knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for

participation in educational, labor and social activities. And they, in turn, manifest themselves in students' attitudes toward nature, society and the individual as a result of upbringing, worldview, and faith. It is expressed by the level of development, abilities, and desire of students to improve physically and mentally. The purpose of teaching biology is due to the factors mentioned above. Knowing the goals of teaching biology gives the teacher the opportunity to control the educational process.

The objectives of the methodology for teaching biology as a science are as follows:

1. Determining the place of pedagogical science in the education and upbringing of students;
2. Develop recommendations for improving school programs and textbooks and apply them in school practice;
3. Determining the content of educational subjects and the sequence of studying subjects in accordance with the age of students;
4. Development of teaching methods and organizational forms taking into account the characteristics of biological subjects;
5. Determination of the necessary equipment for use in the educational process. The biology classroom is a living area, the organization of an experimental site, and the designation of full-scale, visual, dynamic, audio, and video instruments.

Biology is the object of teaching methodology and represents the educational process associated with this subject. The subject of biology teaching methodology is the purpose, content, teaching methods, forms of training and development of students. Research methods for teaching biology:

1. Monitoring the work experience of school teachers and identifying the positive and negative aspects of their activities;
2. Analysis, synthesis and clarification of unsolved problems of data collected in this area, and putting forward the necessary working hypotheses for their solution;
3. Conducting pedagogical experiments in schools and comparing data obtained in experimental and control classes in order to determine how close the hypotheses are to the truth;
4. Analyze, summarize and synthesize data obtained from observations and pedagogical experiments;
5. Based on the information received, create methodological articles, manuals, as well as review and confirm the opinions developed in public schools.

Until now, as a result of pedagogical experiments carried out according to the methodology of teaching biology, “Development of biological concepts”, “System of forms of teaching in biology”, “Methodology of teaching biology”, “Development of environmental concepts in biology”, “Development of biological concepts” have been developed and such theories as “the system of material resources”, “the system of methodological preparation of biology students of pedagogical institutions for school work” were introduced into practice. Depending on the biology subjects taught at school, the subjects “Methodology of teaching biology” are “Methodology of teaching general biology”, “Methodology of teaching botany”, “Methodology of teaching zoology”, “Methodology of teaching man and his health” and, finally, “Methodology teaching.” Methods of General Biology” is divided into special methodological disciplines. The general methodology of teaching biology covers issues such as purpose, objective, content, principles, methods, means, forms, history and stages of teaching biology related to all biological subjects. Special methods are focused on the content of a particular academic subject, for example, lessons related to the age of students, extracurricular activities, excursions, organization of practical and laboratory classes, equipment.

Connection of methods of teaching biology with other subjects. The methodology of teaching biology is closely related to didactics, which is part of pedagogy. If didactics studies the patterns of students acquiring knowledge, skills and competencies, develops theories and principles of teaching all academic subjects at school, then the methodology of teaching biology is related to biology, developing theoretical and practical issues related to the content, forms, methods and means of teaching and learning. The methodology of teaching biology is closely related to psychology.

Because teaching biology is effective only if it corresponds to the age characteristics of students. For example, due to the instability of the attention of adolescents, i.e., grades V-VI, a biology teacher during a lesson uses several techniques to replace students’ activities, and given the specificity of their thinking, more visual aids. used. In high school, since students’ attention has stabilized and they have developed abstract thinking, it is enough to conduct classes more in the form of lectures and use one or two methods. The methodology of teaching biology is inextricably linked with the science of biology.

It contains the basics of almost all areas of biological sciences: botany, zoology, human anatomy and physiology, cytology, biochemistry, embryology,

systematics, ecology, theory of evolution, anthropology, molecular biology. Correct explanation of the external and internal structure of representatives of living nature, the connection of life activity with the external environment, identification of plants, fungi, animals, microorganisms, preparation of micro- and macropreparations from them, observation of them, conducting experiments. a good theory from a teacher requires knowledge and practical training. But the teacher should be well aware that there are important differences between the school subject of biology and the subject of biology

If the main goal of biology is to create new knowledge through research into living and dead nature, then the goal of the school biology curriculum is to give students biological knowledge, that is, biological knowledge in accordance with their age consists of giving concepts, laws, theories and their explanation. In a high school biology course, science is not the science, but the basics of science are the basic information students need. At the same time, a school biology course is not a “small science”, but biology that supports the development and education of students. The system of basic concepts is listed. Methods of teaching biology as an academic subject Methods of teaching biology occupies an extremely important place in the training of biology teachers of general secondary, secondary special, and vocational education. In the process of teaching this subject, the necessary professional knowledge, skills and qualifications for teaching biology are formed. Naturally, in pedagogical science, not all knowledge acquired on a subject is given, but its fundamentals. They consist of educational tasks, a set of specially selected knowledge taking into account the age and level of training of students. Unlike science, the main task of educational science is to provide knowledge and information. Academic science is not an exact copy of science. When creating an educational subject, students are transferred to the system of knowledge and experience accumulated by the subject. This is not only a method of collecting scientific data, but also consists of generalization, clarification of concepts, systematization of scientific facts and opinions. The educational subject, based on its main function of providing knowledge and information, is structured according to a certain procedure. The textbook-methodology for teaching biology in secondary school is closer to science in its structure and content. In addition to scientific information, it also contains various opinions aimed at resolving some controversial issues in science, success or failure of research in the search for truth. In addition, he creates methodology and methods for scientific research.

In the process of theoretical and practical mastery of the methodology of teaching biology, students are not limited to the structure of the school biology course, but also to the organization of teaching biology in general education and secondary specialized vocational institutions, they are introduced to its specific aspects, and are allowed to do so. developing skills in using methods and means of teaching biology, as well as acquiring a minimum set of knowledge that students must master according to the requirements. At the same time, modern pedagogy, the use of information technology and innovative approaches to teaching biology create skills.

References:

1. Saidakhmedov N. Pedagogical skills and pedagogical technology. – Tashkent. MU. 2003.
2. Rizokulovna B.M.T. Methodological manual for teaching biology. Tashkent.2020.
3. Rizokulovna, B.M.T. (2021). EFFECT OF USING MODERN INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES.
4. Golish L.V., Faizullaeva D.M. Design and planning of educational technologies. Tutorial. Edition "Economy"., 2011.

